

PREPARATION OF STUDENTS FOR SOCIAL LIFE BASED ON COOPERATIVE PEDAGOGY AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *In this article, the content of preparing higher education students for social life through cooperative pedagogy, the views of scientists on this, and the relevance and meaning of preparing students for social life through cooperative pedagogy in the course of education are fully disclosed.*

Keywords: *cooperation, higher education students, socialization, upbringing, teaching theory, pedagogical views, pedagogical problem, quality of education, demand and need.*

Introduction

In recent years, under the influence of new approaches to education, the problem of deciding on a technological approach has been researched as an important sign of improving the activities of educational institutions. In addition, the established theory and practice of education shows particularly that the activities of all educational institutions should be improved on a general scientific and methodological basis.

To date, the relevance of the problem of cooperative pedagogy is based on the following:

firstly, the fact that social and pedagogical processes are being rapidly implemented in the educational system in a new and broad sense;

secondly, the state of general, public pedagogical practice (lack of sufficient pedagogical support for teachers and learners, their dissatisfaction with the educational process; insufficient skills of teachers to organize humane and friendly relations with students, etc.);

thirdly, students' great need for new educational innovations.

Literature review

In many research works, the concepts of "cooperation", "partnership", "coordination", "joint action" have been used as synonymous concepts. In our opinion, the concept of "cooperation" is broad and requires joint effective activities to achieve common goals.

As the basis of cooperative pedagogy, high ethical and humanitarian views were reflected in the works of our famous scientists who lived and created during the Central Asian Renaissance in the form of ideas and concrete theories.

Uzbek scientists such as N.Azizkhodzhaeva, J.Yoldoshev, R.Safarova, B.Khodzhaev, Sh.Abdullaeva, and N.Dilova explained the pedagogy of cooperation, the strategies of formation of cooperative activity skills in learners based on mutual friendly relationships.

The analysis of pedagogical and psychological literature (N. Dezhnikova, I. Pervin, V. Dyachenko, D. Johnson, R. Johnson, R. Slavin, etc.) showed that in the organization of group and collective work forms of cooperation the goal set in the mutual activity of subjects ensures effective achievement. As a result of such efficiency, partners move together in educational activities based on the principles of mutual assistance and active cooperation. Therefore, cooperation requires mutual responsibility, friendship, mutual support, mutual respect, mutual sincerity. As a result of active cooperation, learners acquire the skills of conscious and active social partnership, solving social and household tasks in the educational process.

Cooperative pedagogy - in contrast to traditional teaching, focuses on establishing a friendly relationship with the student. Pedagogical activity is organized in the condition of "We" instead of "I", i.e. based on "subject"- "subject" relations. The principle of "working in cooperation" is based on a deep knowledge of the personality of the learner. Before completing educational tasks, a strategic goal is set, and then a sense of self-confidence is formed in the child to fulfill it. In other words, cooperative pedagogy has a positive effect on the student's personality, warmth, cooperation direct one's will to a single goal - education.

According to N. Dilova, pedagogy based on cooperation is a system that represents the joint activity of the teacher and the student, and in this process, the team's creative powers and activity efficiency are manifested. The opportunity to realize new goals is provided. This goal is to teach a group of learners to achieve additional creative results using their strengths. Cooperative pedagogy optimizes the communication process with the help of computer technology with new tools and produces information products. Therefore, cooperative pedagogy uses new educational methods in the processing of educational materials for use in the educational process. To this end, cooperative pedagogy intersects with a number of disciplines. In particular, these include the theory of social communication, information technology, logic, linguistics, as well as personal observations, experimental test results, and knowledge of psychology [4].

The concept of "cooperation" represents the leading concept of modern humanistic pedagogy. Cooperation - in the most general sense, is the interaction of people in work, that is, their joint activity.

G. A. Zukerman said that the essence of cooperation is expressed in the mutual movement of all participants, through which the opportunity to achieve the goal of individual and joint activity arises[11].

Cooperation reflects the main features of joint activity. These include the unity of the goal, the joint cooperation of the participants, the division of the whole process into separate interrelated parts, their distribution among the participants, the coordination and management of individual activities, the existence of a single final result.

The pedagogical essence of cooperation acquires a more precise essence based on S. L. Rubinstein's psychological law of the connection between activity and personality development. [7].

Mutual action is one of the main ways to activate the self-development and self-expression of learners. In the course of cooperative activities, the abilities and opportunities of the learners are revealed even more. By complementing each other, they reach a qualitatively new level of development.

D. B. Elkonin and V. V. Davydov analyzed in their work that all forms of interaction acquire a general character and at the same time require work in small groups, which is reflected in group emotional support. [5].

A. A. Ivin in his scientific studies specifically recognizes that, unlike other relationships, peer relationships are primarily about ensuring mutual equality. Communication with peers provides the student with equal communication, a critical attitude to the thoughts, words and actions of other people, independent of their freedom and desires. To do this, it is necessary to be able to see, evaluate, accept or deny the point of view of other people, and the main thing is to have one's own point of view, outlook, and to protect it.

Analysis and results

It should be noted separately that the educational results are clearly defined in the new requirements for the qualification requirements of the learners. One such requirement is meta-subject outcomes, which require the development of study and collaborative learning skills. It also discusses the expected outcomes of the new qualification requirements. Specifically, these results are expressed in connection with communicative universal learning activities. On the basis of communicative learning activities, learners take into account different opinions, coordinate different points of view in cooperation; reach common solutions in joint activities in case of matching of interests.

Based on these ideas, we can say that these forms of educational organization are of great importance, and the organization of the entire pedagogical process based on cooperative pedagogy serves to improve the quality of education.

It is known that the basis of pedagogical facilitation is the cooperative work of students in groups. Wide attention is paid to the use of individual, group and collective forms of work in connection with the organization of independent work of students. Special importance is attached to the development of communicative competence in students through the formation of cooperation skills. Taking into account such important aspects, the pedagogue scientist B.Kh. Khodzhaev developed the technology of organizing the independent work of the learner by means of pedagogical facilitation[10].

In the monograph of R. G. Safarova on the topic "Strategy of formation of cooperative activity skills in learners based on mutual friendly relations", it is justified that the new conceptual foundations of cooperation help to understand phenomena with certain complexity, including irregularity, gradualism, open systems, society, its various components and education system [8].

As R. G. Safarova noted, learners should do the following to provide pedagogical support to those around them: improving the pedagogical environment; diagnosing the development of learners individually and in groups; giving advice to learners individually and in groups; organization of individual and group development activities for students; carrying out work related to improvement and correction of learners' activities individually and in groups, etc.

Pedagogical cooperation, cooperative approaches, and authoring technologies are reflected in Sh.A.Abdullaeva's instructional manual entitled "Cooperative Pedagogy" [1].

In N.G. Dilova's dissertation on the topic "Improving the mechanisms for the formation of an environment of mutual cooperation in the process of primary education", the formation of cooperation skills in primary education based on a synergistic approach, the teacher's opportunities for organizing the educational process based on cooperation and its development parameters, the content of the pedagogical cooperation process and the principles of its organization, pedagogical forms, ways and methods of creating an atmosphere of cooperation between teachers and students and students and students are highlighted. [4].

E.A. Kopylova's "Educational dialogue as a factor of conscious learning in the process of educating students" explains the forms, types and methods of implementing educational dialogue [9].

As a result of the research, the following criteria and indicators for improving the educational process based on cooperative pedagogy have been determined: the presence of a dialogical description (communicative attitudes of subjects in the process of dialogic relations) in mutual activity in the educational process; the generality of the value-oriented attitude (value-oriented attitude in the mutual activity of subjects in a conscious sense of mutual respect, mutual

trust, mutual understanding, and responsibility) of the subjects in the educational process; compatibility of mutual action of subjects (the ability to set a goal together, plan ways to achieve it, implement the specified measures, jointly control the achievement of the goal, clarify new goals and tasks based on the obtained results); functional-group criteria - intensity of mutual action, emotional-psychological environment in the team.

Components, criteria and indicators of improving the quality of education based on cooperative pedagogy

Components	Criteria	Indicators
Communicative-integrative	Presence of a dialogic description in mutual activity	Communicative attitudes of subjects in the process of dialogic relations
	The generality of the value-oriented attitude of subjects in the educational process	Value-oriented attitude in the mutual activity of subjects in a sense of mutual respect, mutual trust, mutual understanding, and mutual responsibility
Activity-role	Compatibility of mutual action of subjects	The ability to set a goal together, plan ways to achieve it, implement the specified measures, jointly control the achievement of the goal, clarify new goals and tasks based on the obtained results
Individual group	Activity-group criteria	The intensity of mutual action, the positive description of the emotional and psychological environment in the team

On the basis of these criteria and indicators, the levels of improvement of the quality of education (high, medium, low) were determined on the basis of cooperative pedagogy.

A high level of improvement of the educational process on the basis of cooperative pedagogy requires a dialogical description of the mutual action between the subjects, the ability to clearly define the purpose of the activity, plan the methods of achieving it, implement the specified measures, jointly control the achievement of the goal, and focus on value in establishing harmonious relations.

The middle level reflects the altruistic and conforming appearance of mutual action between subjects, the situational character of the ability to determine the purpose of activity, the formal planning of ways to achieve it, the orientation to value in relation to the interests of other subjects.

The low level represents the authoritarian and manipulative character of the mutual action between the subjects, the participation of some subjects in determining the purpose of the activity, the superiority of the personal value system of the subjects over the collective norms.

Conclusion/Recommendations

As a result of the above analysis, it was concluded that systematic planning and pedagogical-psychological support, as well as ensuring the intensity of feedback, openness,

dynamism, statistics of the general pedagogical system, self-development of learners, achievement of activation of intellectual, emotional, moral, cultural and physical capabilities are important in improving the quality and effectiveness of education in higher education.

REFERENCES

1. Абдуллаева Ш.А. Ҳамкорлик педагогикаси. – Т.: Фан ва технология, 2017. – 178 бет.
2. Абу Наср Форобий. Фозил одамлар шахри. –Т.: А.Қодирий номидаги халқ мероси нашриёти, 1993. – 222 б.
3. Сулаймонова Ф. Шарқ ва Ғарб. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 1997. – 415 б.
4. Дилова Н.Ғ. Бошланғич таълимда ўзаро ҳамкорлик муҳитини шакллантириш механизмларини такомиллаштириш: педагогика фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори(PhD). ... дисс. – Нукус, 2018. – 152 с.
5. Давыдов, В.В. Младший школьник как субъект учебной деятельности / В.В. Давыдов, В.И. Слободчиков, Г.И. Цукерман // Вопросы психологии. – 2010.- № 3-4. – С.23.
6. Ивин А.А. Искусство правильно мыслить. – М.: Просвещение, 2010. – 224 с.
7. Рубинштейн С.Л. Принципы и пути развития психологии. – М.: РСФСР. ПФА, 2004. 8-изд. – 180 с.
8. Сафарова Р., Мусаев У.Қ., Мусаев П. ва бошқ. Ўзбекистон Республикасида умумий ўрта таълим стратегияси муаммолари ва таълим мазмунининг янги моделлари, уларни татбиқ этиш йўллари. –Т.: Фан, 2005. – 5 б.
9. Копылова Е.А. Учебный диалог как фактор смыслообразования в процессе обучения старших школьников: дис. ... канд. пед. наук. – Тюмень, 2011. – 185 с.
10. Ходжаев Б.Х. Умумтаълим мактаби ўқувчиларида тарихий тафаккурни модернизациялашган дидактик таъминот воситасида ривожлантириш: Педагогика фанлари доктори. ... дисс. –Т., 2016. – 314 б.
11. Цукерман Г.А. Совместная учебная деятельность как основа формирования умения учиться: автореф. дис. ... докт. психол. наук. – М., 1992. – 39 с.